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Editor's Introduction to the Selected Essays

Contained within a series of six essays provided by members of a seminar dealing specifically with Charles W. Mills' *The Racial Contract*, the reader will find a survey of the diverse ways in which Mills' theory of the Racial Contract finds broad application in our world.

Beginning with Max Holt's *Illuminating the Racial Contract: Citizenship and the Institutionalization of Racialized Labor Markets*, the reader will find the clear ways in which the Racial Contract is an historical actuality within the United States that has clearly manifested itself through the restriction of citizenship from certain groups. Among other factors, Holt's analysis demonstrates the number of ways in which the jurisprudence surrounding the granting of citizenship traditionally revolved around requiring citizens to be "white." The reader will find, however, that this requirement was a moving target, that being one in which the necessary conditions for being classified as "white" within the eyes of the courts was ever changing so as not to include those which the courts desired to exclude.

From there, the reader will find that the Racial Contract did not only exist within our legal system in our distant history, but continues to pervade the American judicial system

ongoingly, especially when it comes to the institution of mass incarceration. In Sarah Edgington's *Where the Racial Contract and the New Jim Crow Collide*, the reader will find the many ways in which incarceration has been used as a method through which the Racial Contract is strictly enforced. Edgington demonstrates that the Racial Contract is not simply a matter of complex political theory, but a material reality that has been borne out of historical actualities. Much like Holt's analysis of the moving target of "whiteness," Edgington analyzes the ways in which the Racial Contract is iteratively rewritten to ensure its longevity even beyond perpetual attempts to bring about its dissolution.

John Hottinger's *Ideal Theory: Helpful Framework or Needless Abstraction?* provides the reader with an understanding of the more theoretical conflicts against which Mills argues. Hottinger provides a clear explanation of the various interpretations of ideal theory before providing an argument for why it is unable to bring us to the finish line, so to speak, in addressing some of the greatest issues of injustice in our world. To do this, Hottinger surveys multiple examples or case studies that package his message quite clearly for the reader.

In my own work, *The Racial Contract and the Case for Epistemic Marxism*, I continue in the line of addressing the theoretical implications of Mills' Racial Contract theory. Concurring with Hottinger's conclusion of the necessity of non-ideal theory in addressing the consequences of the Racial Contract, I establish an original non-ideal theory entitled "Epistemic Marxism." This theory establishes Mills' "epistemology of ignorance" as the leg upon which the current iteration of the Racial Contract stands. Recognizing this, I derive certain principles from traditional Marxist thought in an attempt to demonstrate a potential method through which the Racial Contract may be dissolved.

Catherine Wedin's "*Of One Blood*": *Ethiopian Counter Narrative to the Racial Contract* carries the reader into another area where the Racial Contract is particularly relevant. Through analyzing the novel *Of One Blood* by Pauline Hopkins through the lens of the Racial Contract, Wedin demonstrates some of the ways that the Racial Contract enhances our understanding of the significance and context of cultural artifacts, such as Hopkins' novel.

Lastly, Christian Teigum's *Tocqueville and the Racial Contract* returns to the theme of historical analysis as Teigum engages with the works of Alexis de Tocqueville to determine to what degree he may, in fact, be one of the earliest critical race theorists. Along the way, Teigum provides an interesting analysis of Tocqueville's thoughts surrounding democracy in America and the historical and cultural context out of which Tocqueville's words were produced.

Ultimately, these six essays provide only a glimpse into the potential applications of Mills' theory of the Racial Contract. In presenting this series of works to the reader, the Luther Political Review hopes to spark further thought and discussion surrounding Mills' theories and how we as a world, country, and community can address the intricacies and complexities brought on by his influential work. In this way, we hope to honor his life and his work.